

Damage Detection of Composite Plate using Finite Element Analysis based on Structural Health Monitoring

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SUMMARY

Delamination in composite structures plays a major role in lowering structural strength and stiffness, consequently downgrading system integrity and reliability. The aim of this paper is to show that Lamb waves may be effectively generated using piezoelectric transducers embedded inside a composite plate for health monitoring application. A Lamb wave-based quantitative identification technique for delamination in VARTM composite structures was established. Propagation of Lamb waves in composite plates was evaluated using dynamic FEM analysis. Then, an experiment is carried out to verify the validity of the analytical study based on finite element models. The study was carried out to assess damages in composite plate by fusing information from multiple sensing paths of the embedded network. It was based on the Hilbert transform, signal correlation and probabilistic searching. The obtained results show that satisfactory detection of defects could be achieved by proposed method

Keywords: Finite element analysis, Health Monitoring, Hilbert transform

1. Introduction

Composite materials have been widely used in many high performance structures due to their high specific strength and stiffness coupled with cost effectiveness over traditional materials [1]. When the composite material structures are damaged, the appearance of the structures has visibly perfect surface. However, internal damages such as microcracks and delaminations are generated, they can eventually cause catastrophic failures of structures during the service life. Therefore, composite structures are needed to be examined frequently. One of the disadvantages of the current inspection techniques is that the structures have to be taken out of service for inspection. The current inspection techniques are inconvenient and inefficient. Furthermore those are not suitable to apply to the structures that are currently in service. Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques based on Lamb wave propagation have been subject of study for several decades. Lamb waves, the elastic waves in plate-like structures, can propagate over a relatively long distance, even in materials with high attenuation ratios, allowing a broad area to be interrogated using only a few transducers. With high sensitivity to both surface and embedded structural damage, Lamb waves have been

widely used to develop various damage identification approaches for delamination, holes, cracks, etc., in both composite and metallic materials [2-5] Lin and Yuan [6, 7] studied Lamb wave propagation in plates integrated with piezoelectric sensor/actuators analytically and experimentally, employing Mindlin plate theory and considering the effects of transverse shear and rotary inertia in the host plates. PZT disk actuators were mounted symmetrically on the surface of plates, the piezoelectric effect of PZT disks was introduced as an equivalent bending moment, and thus the A_0 mode of Lamb wave was generated and collected. Grondel *et al.* [8] extended the coupled finite element-normal expansion method and developed an experimental technique to optimally generate the A_0 mode of Lamb wave in a composite plate using surface-bonded piezoceramic transducers, which was further applied for damage detection.

In this study, a practical and effective real time damage identification approach was developed for woven-glass/phenol composite plates. The feasibility of this system was verified by applying it to the composite plates for detection of known localized damage. The comparisons between experimental and analytical studies for damage detection on composite plate were made. Then, an experiment is carried out to verify the validity of the analytical study based on finite element models. A feasibility study was carried out to locate and gauge damage in VATRM composites by using data from multiple sensing paths of the embedded network, based on the Hilbert transform.

2. Delamination in composite plate

Laminated composite structures are highly susceptible to low-velocity impact, resulting in invisible damage, manifesting itself as fibre breakage, matrix cracking or local delaminating [9]. In particular, delaminating, appearing as the debonding of adjoining plies, is the most hazardous defect for laminated composites, which could be induced during careless manufacture or a consequence of accidental impact. The occurrence of delamination considerably lowers structural strength, stiffness and severely reduces structural integrity. Focusing on the delamination in carbon fibre-reinforced composite laminates, both theoretical studies [10, 11] and numerical simulation [12, 13] have been well developed, where one- or two-dimensional assumptions on delamination were normally applied during modeling. In this study, however, aimed at a higher simulation precision, a three dimensional full-scale FEM modeling technique was herein developed.

3. Procedure for evaluating delamination

In non-destructive evaluation (NDE), a common understanding is that the ultrasonic scanning technique can usually detect damage with a characteristic size larger than one-half of the wavelength of ultrasonic wave. For this reason, the fundamental anti-symmetrical mode (A_0) is preferable and more sensitive to damage because its wavelength is shorter than that of the S_0 mode at the same frequency. However, the A_0 mode exhibits more severe dispersion at low frequencies and more stringent experimental configurations are normally required to prevent energy leakage for its substantial out-of-plane vibrations. In contrast, the mode shape of the S_0 mode is simple and the stresses are almost uniform throughout the thickness of the plate at low products of frequency and plate thickness, up to 1MHzmm [14]. Therefore, unlike the previous

studies, we excite two modes for quantitative evaluation and comparison since both S_0 and A_0 modes have advantages and disadvantages in defect scanning.

3.1 Explicit dynamic analysis using *FEM*

Explicit dynamic analysis is computationally efficient for the analysis of large models with relatively short dynamic response times and is ideally suited for analyzing high-speed dynamic events [15]. The explicit central-difference time integration rule satisfies the dynamic equilibrium equations at the beginning of each increment, t ; the accelerations calculated at time, t , are used to advance the velocity solution to time $t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}$ while the displacement solution is applied to time $t + \Delta t$. The equations of motion for the body are integrated as

$$\dot{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \dot{u}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{\Delta t_{i+1} + \Delta t_i}{2} \ddot{u}_i \quad (1)$$

and

$$u_{i+1} = u_i + \Delta t_{i+1} \dot{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector and subscript i refers to the increment number in an explicit dynamic step.

The central-difference operator is conditionally stable, and the stability limit (with or without damping) is given in terms of the cyclical frequency of excitation f as [15]

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{2}{f} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{2}{f} \left(\sqrt{1 + \xi^2} - \xi_{\max} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where ξ_{\max} is the fraction of critical damping in the mode with the highest frequency. Introducing damping to the solution reduces the stable time increment, and in the ABAQUS/Explicit FEM code a small amount of damping is introduced in the form of bulk viscosity to control high frequency oscillations. An approximation to the stability limit is often introduced as the smallest transit time of a dilatational wave across any element in a FE model

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{L_{\min}}{C_d} \quad (5)$$

Where L_{\min} is the smallest element dimension in the FE model and C_d is the dilatational wave speed defined by the effective Lamé's constants [15].

The mesh for a FE model is dependent on the minimum wavelength of elastic wave propagating in the model. From the dispersion curves, the wavelength of elastic wave decreases with an increase in frequency. There is a maximum allowable dimension of elements for the selected frequency of elastic wave propagation. Let L_{\max} represent the

maximum intermodal interval of elements in a FE mesh, n_{\min} the minimum number of intermodal intervals per wave length [15], and C_{\min} the minimum group velocity of elastic wave, the requirement for L_{\max} is then expressed as

$$L_{\max} < \frac{\lambda_{\min}}{n_{\min}} = \frac{C_{\min}}{n_{\min} f} \quad (6)$$

In the present analysis, n_{\min} is chosen as 5-8 to assure the correct convergence of the explicit dynamic procedure.

3.2 Model of delaminated plate

A 4-ply VARTM composite plate, shaped at $0.187 \times 0.187 \times 0.019 \text{ m}^3$, was considered and schematically shown in Fig. 1. The mechanical properties of the VARTM specimen are listed in Table. 1 In the delaminated region, a volume-split was formed by separating two delamination surfaces with the distance of half thickness of an individual lamina, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For accurate simulation of the wave propagation, the model was finely meshed using 8-node 3-D brick elements, with four layers of elements in the plate thickness corresponding to four laminae. At least 10 elemental nodes were allocated within the Lamb wave wavelength, to guarantee the validity of the simulated dynamic responses. Such a mesh density leads to approximately 30,000 elements in total for the delaminated plate. A surface contact algorithm [15] was introduced to process the contact problem arising from delamination, primarily relaxing restrictions on two contactable surfaces. The contact algorithm permits a small relative sliding displacement and arbitrary rotation of two delaminated surfaces. Both the upper and lower delamination surfaces were defined using an element-based deformable surface [15], allowing the interaction between two surfaces in the normal direction, but resisting mutual penetration. A full-scale FEM model for the VARTM specimen was created using HYPERMESH platform.

Table 1 Material properties of VARTM specimen

$E_{11}(\text{GPa})$	$E_{22}(\text{GPa})$	$E_{33}(\text{GPa})$	$G_{12}(\text{GPa})$	ν_{12}	ν_{21}	$\rho(\text{g/cm}^3)$
20	20	5	2.49	0.08	0.08	2.00

Fig. 1 Specimen configurations in FEM and experiment

Fig. 2 Modeling for delamination

3.3 FEM simulation

Lamb wave was numerically generated in the delaminated plate. A previous study [4] has verified that the Lamb wave with a waveform of 5-cycle sinusoid tone bursts windowed by the *Hanning* function that can benefit the signal identification. It also effectively prevents wave dispersion and makes the signal interpretation explicit. In this study, PZT discs transducers were chosen as transmitters and receivers since they can exhibit simultaneous actuator and sensor behavior. Lamb wave was activated at a central frequency of 0.265 MHz, by evenly applying a horizontal displacement on all the nodes in the thickness at the plate, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The generated Lamb wave is exhibited in Fig. 3 with its frequency spectrum via fast Fourier transform (FFT), where majority of the energy is observed to centralise around 0.265 MHz. Lamb wave propagation in the delaminated laminate was simultaneously monitored at a sample rate of 10.24 MHz. With a time step for dynamic calculation less than the ratio of the minimum distance of any two adjoining nodes to the maximum Lamb wave velocity in the excitation frequency range, the dynamic simulation was conducted using ABAQUS/Explicit. Due to the absence of an element type with piezoelectric function in ABAQUS/Explicit, a specific modeling technique for PZT actuator model and sensor has been introduced [16]. In the actuator model, a uniform radial displacement in the x - y plane was applied to all the nodes along the edge of the actuator, to generate the fundamental symmetric and anti-symmetric Lamb wave mode. Actuation case was applied to study the interaction of Lamb wave modes with a delamination. A single PZT actuator embedded of the plate was simulated by applying both shear force and bending moment to generate the S_0 and A_0 modes simultaneously [17].

Fig. 3 Input excitation signals at (a) time domain (b) frequency domain

3.4 Experimental characterization

A specimen with the same geometry, mechanical properties and boundary conditions as that in the FEM simulation was experimentally evaluated. Figure 4 illustrates the active real-time structural health monitoring system developed in this study. In this system, PZT discs transducers with a circular shape (Kyungwon Inc.) were chosen as transmitters and receivers since they can exhibit simultaneous actuator and sensor behavior. Transducer arrays in each region were used to measure the group velocity. A function generator (Ram-10000, Ritec) was used to excite the transmitting actuators. The applied excitation signal was five cycles of a 0.265 MHz sinusoidal tone burst enclosed in a *Hanning* window. The received signals were collected on a digital oscilloscope (CS225, Gage Inc). The validity of this system was carried out with the four layer woven-glass/phenol laminate plate with predetermined delamination. The Teflon tape with length of 69 mm and width of 15.5 mm was inserted between the second and third layers to simulate the common delamination. The center of the delamination lies 72.5 mm and 72.5 mm respectively away from the left edge and bottom edge of the laminate plate. The received signals were acquired at a sampling rate of 2.0 MS/s by the digital oscilloscope, which averaged 32 samples in order to improve the S/N ratio. The central frequency of the transmitting signal was 0.265 MHz. However, the central frequencies of the received signals, when Lamb waves were propagated with in each region, did not correspond with this value. In other words, there was a deviation from the central frequency of the transmitting signal. All the signal analysis were performed with a MatLab Platform.

Fig. 4 Schematic drawing of experimental setup

4. Hilbert Transform

Wave propagation in an elastic medium is the transportation of energy, and the interaction of waves with structural damage can significantly influence their propagation properties, accompanying with the energy reflection, transmission, and mode conversion. For example, when incipient symmetric mode encounters damage, a new mode, anti-symmetric mode, anti-symmetric, is generated, in addition to the transmitted and reflected symmetric mode waves. Differences in the location and severity of damage may produce unique energy scattering phenomena. Therefore, the energy of the response signals contains ample information about the damage. On the basis of such observations, denoised Lamb wave signals were evaluated in terms of their distribution in the time domain through the Hilbert transform. For an arbitrary signal, $s(t)$, the Hilbert transform is defined as [18]

$$H(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{s(t')}{t-t'} dt' \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) performs a 90° phase shift or quadrature filter to construct a so-called analytic signal $S_A(t)$.

$$S_A(t) = s(t) + iH(t) = e(t)e^{i\phi(t)} \quad (9)$$

where

$$e(t) = \sqrt{s^2(t) + H^2(t)} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\phi(t) = \arctan \frac{H(t)}{s(t)} \quad (11)$$

whose real part is the original signal $s(t)$ itself and whose imaginary part is its corresponding Hilbert transform $H(t)$. $E(t)$ is the module of the analytic signal and $\phi(t)$ is the instantaneous phase. The envelope curve of $e(t)$ in equation (3) depicts the energy distribution of s in the time domain.

5. Results

Figure 5 shows the Lamb wave propagation of four layer composite plates with and without the delamination. In numerical and experiments, the group velocities of Lamb wave modes excited by PZT sensors can be determined in the signals from the specimens without delamination, by calculating time of flight between a pair of transducers at a certain distance. As the fastest mode, the S_0 mode arrives prior to all the available Lamb wave modes in the time sequence. The theoretical dispersion curves for the group velocity were derived using formalism of Nayfeh *et al* [19]. The dispersion curves shows that there can be two modes (S_0 , A_0) at 0.265 MHz in Fig. 6. The group velocities are 3.2 km/s for S_0 mode, and 1.1 Km/s A_0 at 0.265 MHz center frequency. Considering the specimen, the group velocities of only two Lamb wave modes could be detected in specimens without delamination, because they are non-dispersive in this range. Figure 7 shows normalized amplitude signals with and without delamination. Good correlation between the numerical and experiment result is observed for the incipient S_0 and A_0 mode with discrepancy in propagation velocity being less than 5% only. In Fig. 7, two modes are clearly identified as the S_0 and A_0 modes. The normal displacement amplitude of the S_0 mode is in fact twice larger than that of the A_0 mode. This quantitative result is well agreed with the theory as indicated in Fig. 6. However, if the delamination is presented in the Lamb wave paths, the signals show significant changes. It is also well indicated in Fig. 7. Therefore, it is possible to judge the presence of internal defects by monitoring the changes of received signals. The amplitude, shape and length of wave form in the time domain of acquired signals were changed significantly. Figure 8 shows the Hilbert transform of signals in their paths of 0.265 MHz center frequency sensors with and without delamination. It can be inspected that energy of A_0 mode is decreased and that of S_0 mode is decreased more, compared with energy of the two modes in Fig. 8, due to the delamination. Thus even if the sensor in

lower than cut-off frequency is selected, it is known that the center frequency appropriate to each specimen should be determined experimentally. It is also shown that S_0 mode more effective than A_0 mode in the delamination.

Fig. 5 Lamb wave propagation in terms of U_3 at 4.95×10^{-5} sec

Fig. 6 Dispersion curves for group velocity in the VARTM specimen

Fig. 7 Normalized amplitudes of Lamb wave without and with delamination (a) FEM (without delamination), (b) Experimental (without delamination), (c) FEM (with delamination), (d) Experimental (with delamination)

Fig. 8 Energy distributions for the signals with and without delamination using Hilbert transform: (a) without delamination (b) with delamination

6. Conclusions

Delamination is a common damage widely found in the advanced composite structures. In this study, an embeddable active PZT sensor network was developed, and designed to increase the functionality and reliability of damage assessment and to condition monitoring of the composite structures. The propagation characteristics of Lamb waves generated and collected by the embedded sensor network were numerically and experimentally evaluated. According to the analytical result of numerical study using finite element models showed successful damage prediction results with a consistent trend of experimental study. Numerical and experimental investigations show the possibility of the S_0 mode becomes dominant over the A_0 mode propagating in VARTM specimen. Results show that the embedded sensor network presents particular immunity to environmental noise, excellent stability and repeatability in data acquisition, when compared with traditional surface bonded PZT sensors approaches. The generated wave exhibits non-dispersive properties under an excitation frequency of 0.265 MHz for VARTM specimen. A feasibility study was conducted, using the embedded sensor network for damage in VARTM specimen, on the basis of Hilbert transform. It is shown that good diagnostic results can be achieved with current method. The Hilbert transform is possible method for the detection of the presence of delamination in composite plates. The excellent identification capability demonstrated the significant potential of such a technique in improving the integrity of composite structures.

6. Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Korea Foundation for International Cooperation of Science & Technology (KICOS) through a grant provided by the Korean Ministry of Education, Science & Technology (MEST) in 2007 (No. K20704000090) and the Aerospace Material Technology Development funded by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy, Republic of Korea.

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